

SIGNS OF RADICALIZATION – THE EXAMPLE OF ҲИЗБ АЛ-ТАҲРӢР

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Abstract: this work includes research on the essence of radicalization and its impact on socio-political life. It analyzes the initial stages of radicalization, the process of indoctrination, and methods of inclining members towards new ways of thinking using the Ҳизб ал-ТаҳрӢр organization as an example. The research findings identify the main stages of radicalization, including the incorporation of group ideologies into individuals and the formation of a "party personality." Additionally, it emphasizes the necessity of enhancing measures against radicalization and effective prevention against extremist ideas, which will strengthen scientific foundations aimed at protecting youth from harmful influences.

Keywords: radicalization, Ҳизб ал-ТаҳрӢр, indoctrination, cell system, extremism, youth radicalization, religious fundamentalism.

Despite the extensive collection of new information about members of Ҳизб ал-ТаҳрӢр and their activities, understanding the precise mechanisms of radicalization remains challenging, as radicalization is a complex process that does not follow a straightforward path. Therefore, it is essential to clarify the concept of radicalization itself, as grasping this notion is critical before delving deeper into the subject.

The transformation within Ҳизб ал-ТаҳрӢр relies heavily on a deep process of radicalization that plays a central role in reshaping individuals' perspectives. Through this process, individuals are encouraged to adopt a new worldview. According to social cognitive theory, a person's behavior is shaped by their inner feelings and the influence of their surrounding environment. Social psychologists have long been interested in how fundamental cognitive and motivational changes occur in individuals who become members of a groupve environment exists within radical groups to foster this new way of thinking, as members are generally willing to conform to the group's requirements. In this process, a strong connection develops between the individual and the group, which aids Ҳизб ал-ТаҳрӢр in altering its members' beliefs and perspectives [1].

The process of embedding Ҳизб ал-ТаҳрӢр's worldview within an individual's mind is essentially about adopting certain concepts and behaviors that integrate external aspects of the world into the internal mindset. This internal mindset,

strengthened by the influence of group participation, begins to impose behavioral constraints and actively reshape the individual's perception of the outside world. In other words, when a new member joins *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr*, their views on others gradually align with the organization's perspective, allowing them to internalize the collective ideology of *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr*.

The process of adopting ideas and beliefs is actively shaped through a process of socialization, which profoundly alters the individual's character and fosters a sense of loyalty to the group. This transformation is not merely superficial; it embeds the group's ideals deeply within the individual, aligning their personal values and motivations with the group's objectives [2]

Despite the accumulation of numerous new insights about members of *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr* and their activities, understanding the precise mechanisms of radicalization remains challenging, as radicalization is a complex process that doesn't follow a straightforward path. Therefore, it is essential to define the concept of radicalization itself, as a clear understanding is necessary before delving deeply into the subject.

In *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr*, the process of transforming a person's identity is heavily reliant on deep-rooted radicalization, which plays a central role in altering the individual's worldview. Through this process, individuals are encouraged to adopt a new way of perceiving the world. According to social cognitive theory, a person's behavior is shaped by internal feelings and the influence of their environment. Social psychologists have long been interested in understanding how core cognitive and motivational changes occur in individuals who are part of a group. Groups like *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr* create an environment conducive to developing new forms of thinking because members are generally willing to adapt to the group's requirements. In this process, a strong bond forms between the individual and the group, aiding *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr* in reshaping members' beliefs and perspectives.

The process of embedding *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr*'s worldview into a person's mind involves internalizing specific concepts and behaviors, where external characteristics of the world are integrated into one's internal perspective. This internal framework, strengthened by the influence of group participation, becomes powerful enough to impose behavioral constraints and actively reshape the individual's view of the outside world. When a new member joins *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr*, their views on others begin to align with the group's perspective, enabling them to assimilate the collective ideology of *Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr*. The process of internalizing ideas and beliefs is actively shaped through socialization, which

profoundly transforms the individual's character and fosters a strong sense of loyalty to the group.

The development of a "Ḥizbī personality"—a common identity specific to the group—serves as a crucial stage in Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr's radicalization process, integrating the individual into the group and forming a new cognitive and behavioral disposition. This is especially significant when the group presents itself as the sole interpreter of radical ideology. Within the group environment, new members are indoctrinated to think in alignment with the group's viewpoint. This leads to a redefined way of seeing the social world, often clashing with existing conventions and norms [4].

The radicalization process within Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr not only reorients individuals' beliefs but also reshapes their identities to align closely with the group's ideology, creating a strong bond and collective identity that reinforces the group's radical perspective.

The radicalization process within Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr is primarily aimed at integrating the individual into the group, transforming their thought patterns and behaviors to align with the group's ideology. New members are systematically taught to think in a way that reflects the group's perspective, leading them to view the social world through a new, distinct lens. During this process, the individual abandons traditional beliefs and adopts the radical ideology of the group.

Under the influence of the group, members begin to identify closely with their fellow members, while accentuating the distinctions that separate them from "others." These interactions foster a sense of belonging, aligning the individual's identity with the collective views of the group. Consequently, members not only accept the group's ideas but feel compelled to express and act upon them, even if they have personal doubts.

In the process of socialization, Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr targets disillusioned youth who may feel marginalized or dissatisfied, as these individuals tend to show higher motivation toward the group's ideology [5]. According to Bakri, issues like racism are often exploited to reach out to young people who have encountered such challenges in their childhood. These psychological wounds are used as a means to drive them toward radicalization in adulthood.

Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr seeks to recruit young Muslims who are struggling due to societal issues, such as racial discrimination and cultural conflicts. These experiences lead young people to seek a sense of belonging within a group that offers solidarity and purpose. Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr capitalizes on this need, shaping

these individuals with its ideology, providing them with a new identity and purpose. This process aims to redefine their roles in society, transforming them into active and loyal members of the group.

Members of Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr view their organization as unique, as it operates under well-established guidelines and stringent standards controlled by the leadership. These standards enable the leaders of Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr to assign roles and tasks at each stage of involvement, but they also limit the ability of new members to understand the broader context of their activities or develop independent thinking. This structured approach fosters conformity and reinforces loyalty to the organization, while minimizing individual autonomy and critical thought.

Radicalization within Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr operates as a group-driven activity, directed by an indoctrinator and conducted in what is known as the “halqa” (circle). The halqa is the organization’s primary method of educating new members and instilling its ideology. Conducted in small groups, the halqa involves regular study sessions where participants delve into the principles and objectives of Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr, gradually adapting to the group’s beliefs and preparing for active participation within society.

Upon joining the halqa, new members may initially hold conventional beliefs about society and life, but as they engage with other new recruits, their previous views are broken down and replaced by Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr’s ideological perspective. As noted by J. Wilson in *Concepts of Indoctrination: Philosophical Essays*, beliefs implanted by high-status figures can replace one’s original thoughts, intensifying the radicalization process. Similarly, D. Wining suggests in *The Manipulated Mind: Conditioning, Control, and Indoctrination* that new members may be unaware of the halqa's true purpose, suggesting that manipulation could prevent them from fully understanding the group’s goals and operations. Wining posits that, due to this manipulation, new members are deprived of critical thinking, hindering their comprehension of the organization’s ultimate objectives. In practice, many new members voluntarily join the halqa, which demonstrates the complexity of the indoctrination process: while some members may not fully grasp the objectives and mechanisms, they willingly accept the group’s ideology.

According to R. Lifton in *Thought Reform and the Psychology of Totalism: A Study of Brainwashing in China*, manipulation alone is not sufficient to gain full control over an individual’s mind. This suggests that manipulation might not completely characterize the halqa process, where the aim is not to create

“mindless automatons” but to develop individuals with strong ideological convictions. The objective is to reshape new members' thoughts and behaviors in alignment with Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr's ideology, cultivating individuals who can independently defend and further these ideas [6].

In the “continuation” phase of radicalization, interaction outside the halqa becomes necessary to deepen the influence on new members. In the 1980s, ‘Umar Bakrī recognized the importance of extending influence beyond the two-hour halqa meetings by observing and interacting with new members outside the sessions. Mentors established connections with members outside the halqa to monitor how they implemented Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr's ideals in their lives. During this period, mentors dedicated additional time to explaining religious beliefs and ideological concepts in depth, especially for new recruits. The primary goal of this stage was to transform the halqa into a unified and cohesive community.

This doctrination highlights Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr's focus on fostering loyalty and deep ideological commitment. By balancing structured group sessions with personal mentorship, Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr reinforces its principles and ensures that its members internalize and actively promote the organization's views.

New members of Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr are encouraged to participate in a deep socialization process within a peer group environment, receiving social and ideological support. Through this process, new recruits gradually absorb the ideas of Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr and remain loyal to them. Observations indicate that new members actively engage with their peer group, strengthening their connections within it. This collective “spirit” fosters a strong sense of community, which enhances the long-term influence and impact of the radicalization process [7]. Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr 's ideology becomes a central part of members' lives, instilling a new cognitive worldview that deepens their commitment to the organization, making it difficult for them to imagine life outside the group. Radicalization is not merely an individual process; it is situated within the context of group influence halqa, Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr educates new members with a specific ideological worldview that shapes their perspective on society and their response to it. Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr presents this activity as an intellectual endeavor, but as a political movement, it aims to bring about social change, requiring ideologically trained activists. The halqa is the central mechanism through which Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr indoctrinates its ideology. As noted in Passmore's *Concepts of Indoctrination: Philosophical Essays*, radicalization can be seen as a form of “special instruction” that, in the case of Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr, involves “imprinting” ideology onto new members

This research paper has analyzed the nature of the radicalization process and its impact on social and political life. Using Ḥizb al-Taḥrīr as a case study, the early stages of radicalization, the indoctrination process, and the transformation of group members towards new ways of thinking have been explored. The findings highlight the main stages of radicalization: developing new ideas, embedding group ideology within the individual, and forming a “Ḥizbī identity.” The study underscores the urgency of counter-radicalization efforts, emphasizing the need to strengthen preventive measures against extremist ideologies. A deeper understanding of the radicalization process contributes to the development of scientific foundations aimed at protecting young people from harmful influences that could poison their minds.

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